

The Didache

Secondary source

Entered by Joshua Schachterle, Independent Scholar

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Early Christianity, Religious Group, Koine Greek Text, Text, Jewish Christians

The full title of the document is The Teaching of the Lord through the Twelve Apostles to the Nations (Διδαχή Κυρίου διὰ τῶν δώδεκα ἀποστόλων τοῖς ἔθνεσιν). The Didache is an early church document, but is distinctly Jewish in some ways, as well, and seems to show how a Jewish Christian community adapted its practices and procedures for gentile Christians (the nations). It has been dated as early as the late 1st century CE (Milavec) and as late as the early 2nd century CE (Niederwimmer). It includes three major sections: the first on ethics, the second on rituals, and the third on group or church organization. The community within which this document was (anonymously) produced was likely located in Antioch, Syria and it shares material with the Gospel of Matthew which was probably also produced there. There is some disagreement among scholars about which whether the Didache depends on Matthew or Matthew on the Didache, or whether they both depend on another source. Some facets of this document, the description of the Eucharist, for example, differ markedly from that of Paul's letters and the canonical gospels. The Didache seems to indicate that Jesus's death and resurrection were not the focal point of orthodoxy for this community, but rather ethical and ritual practices.

Date Range: 50 CE - 110 CE

Region: Antioch, Syria

Region tags: Syria, Antioch

Antioch was the third largest city within the Roman Empire in the 1st century CE. It was a major center of Second Temple Judaism and a foundational center for early Christianity as well.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Niederwimmer, Kurt., and Harold W. Attridge. *The Didache: A Commentary*. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1998.

— Source 2: Milavec, Aaron. *The Didache: Faith, Hope, & Life of the Earliest Christian Communities, 50-70 C.E.*. New York: Newman Press, 2003.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ccel.org/ccel/lake/fathers2/fathers2.v.html>
- Source 1 Description: This is an online Koine Greek version of the Didache.
- Source 2 URL: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1476993X19838107>
- Source 2 Description: Online article summarizing thirty-five years of Didache scholarship.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.jewishencyclopedia.com/articles/5181-didache>
- Source 3 Description: An article on the Didache from the Jewish Encyclopedia

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.embarl.force9.co.uk/Other/Dida.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: This is an interlinear (Koine Greek/English) translation of the Didache.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Methods of Composition

- Written

Notes: There are no original manuscripts of the Didache. A 10th century manuscript written on papyrus was discovered in 1873 by Philotheos Bryennios. This is the oldest extant manuscript.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: While many scholars believe that the material was compiled from several sources, Milavec believes it was written as one coherent document.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

- No

Materiality

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Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: There is no indication of a patron, whether an individual or a polity, funding the production of this document. One could infer that the community for which it is written funded its production but there is no explicit evidence of this.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no way to know this from the text. Scholarly estimates of how large the Didache community was vary widely.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: While the document never indicates that members should actively recruit others for their community, they are clearly open to Jews and Gentiles joining the group. There are induction procedures for new members, for example, involving baptism and following precepts.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The Didache was not intended as Scripture. However, it was considered by some to be part of the biblical canon. The Ethiopian Orthodox church still considers it canonical, although most modern churches do not. Thus, while it is generally not considered Scripture, it does contain scriptural teachings and is a foundational religious document, at least for the Jewish and Gentile Christians to whom and for whom it is written.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The text is written in Koine Greek which was the main language spoken in that region at that time. However, recall that the entire New Testament is also written in Koine Greek. In that sense the language, drawing also upon the Septuagint (Greek version of the Hebrew Bible) might be considered a religious language.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious

study of text?

– No

Notes: This could be the case but there is no evidence for it in the text itself.

Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is highly likely that many of the sources for this text rely on oral traditions about Jesus, the apostles, and other facets foundational to Christianity.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: There is no indication that the text itself must be read or even be present in the context of ritual. However, it describes the correct way to perform rituals and so it certainly might have been used during rituals in order to maintain correct practice.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: The significance seems to reside in the meaning of the text rather than its material form.

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Given the context of Second Temple Judaism and Early Christianity, there was likely a spirit-body distinction but the text is not explicit about this.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: It is clear that the Two Ways spoken of in the first section of the document speak of those who adhere to prosocial norms (who will be rewarded) and those who do not (who will be

punished). The text says that at the eschaton, "then shall the creation of men come into the fire of trial, and many shall be made to stumble and shall perish; but those who endure in their faith shall be saved from under the curse itself."

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Performance of rituals such as prayer, baptism, and the Eucharist absolutely matter to the deity, but there are no sacrificial offerings.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

Notes: The Didache says "And concerning food, bear what you are able; but against that which is sacrificed to idols be exceedingly careful; for it is the service of dead gods. (6.3) "Bear what you are able" means to adhere as much as possible to the halakhic food laws, showing that the Torah is still important to this community.

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: The document makes explicit reference to the prohibition on murder from the decalogue (2:2). It also cautions against anger because it can lead to murder, although coreligionists as victims are not specified (3:2).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: The commandment is simply not to murder anyone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: Reference to this prohibition from the decalogue is made.

↳ Incest

– No

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Fornication and pederasty are explicitly forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: In the decalogue section the document prohibits lying (2:5).

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: "Your speech shall not be false, nor empty, but fulfilled by deed (2:5)."

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: There is a reference to new members who either need to have a trade while living in the community or, if they have no trade, must agree to do whatever work the community thinks necessary (12:3-4)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is prohibited in 5:1.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: No references to elders in terms of age, but certainly chapter 11 says to respect true prophets, bishops, and deacons.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Notes: 2:3 repeats the decalogues prohibition on bearing false witness and speaking badly of anyone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Notes: Again from the decalogue, stealing is prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: The document seems to imply that the deity only expects adherents to do their best: "For if you are able to bear the entire yoke of the Lord [the Torah], you will be perfect; but if you are not able to do this, do what you are able (6:2)."

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: These include baptism, fasting, prayer, and the eucharist.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly demonstrated in the injunction to give to the poor (1:6)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: There four chapters on rituals and how to perform them correctly (7-10). These include baptism, fasting, prayer, and the Eucharist. However, the Didache makes provisions for those who want to perform the rituals but cannot do so perfectly because of adverse conditions. There are, for example, suggestions for different ways to practice baptism when the optimal conditions, flowing water, are not present.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text forbids adultery and fornication, but says nothing about sex within marriage.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The 10 commandments are invoked in chapter 2, along with more specific rules in chapter 1.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: In chapter 16, there are simply signs that will appear when he is about to return.

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The lineage established is certainly Jewish, in the sense that the decalogue and other notions like the Two Ways discourse from Jewish tradition are mentioned. However, there is also a second lineage from Jesus, and many of the ethical commands share material with the Sermon on the Mount. Interestingly, unlike in Matthew, none of the commands are explicitly attributed to Jesus. They are instead simply part of the community rule.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The final section of the Didache is a kind of church organization. First in authority are wandering apostles and/or prophets. There are criteria listed for discerning whether these are real or false prophets: If they stay more than two days, act contrary to their teachings, or ask for money they are false prophets. Next are bishops and deacons appointed by the community.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Spiritual Elect

Notes: Prophets and apostles are not permanent parts of the community. Bishops and deacons, however, are chosen by community members. They must be people who are "gentle, not money-loving, truthful, and tested (15:1)."

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The last line of the Didache says "Then the world will see the Lord coming upon the clouds of heaven." So while the spatial location of God's realm is above the earth, the afterlife will be heaven coming down to earth.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

Notes: While heaven is above, in the afterlife it will come down to earth.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: There is no specified time but the time of the approaching eschaton will be indicated by signs such as a "world-deceiver" coming and the resurrection of the righteous (16:4).

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

Notes: Since adultery and sex outside marriage (fornication) are prohibited, we can assume that monogamy is allowed.

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Notes: The text does not specify (or even address) marriage, but since adultery and fornication are forbidden, we can assume that monogamy is encouraged.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: Eating food offered to idols was a general cultural practice in the Roman world, but the Didache community are told not to do it.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: The common Jewish discourse of the Two Ways, one good and one evil, are invoked by listing what each one does in Chapter 1.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Again, see the reproduced decalogue in chapter 2.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: This community believes that their deity is universal and thus all norms prescribed by the deity should be followed by everyone, even though this document is specifically written only for the community.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Again, signs will appear indicating the imminent end of the age.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: The community is told to look for certain signs: "For in the last days false prophets and corrupters shall be multiplied, and the sheep shall be turned into wolves, and love shall be turned into hate; for when lawlessness increases, they shall hate and persecute and betray one another, and then shall appear the world-deceiver as Son of God, and shall do signs and wonders, and the earth shall be delivered into his hands, and he shall do iniquitous things which have never yet come to pass since the beginning (16:3-4).

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Not much is said explicitly about this, but the righteous will live or be resurrected if they have died and the unrighteous will die or stay dead.

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Notes: This is implied in the coming of the Lord and the resurrection of the faithful, although the language of "restoration of the world" is not used. See 16:7-8.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Specifically those who have remained faithful (16:5).

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Again, those who have remained faithful.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment seems to be that the unrighteous shall simply remain dead rather than being resurrected (16:7).

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: There are not multiple versions per se, but several early Christian documents including the Apostolic Constitutions and the Didascalia Apostolorum draw directly from it.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is debated by scholars. The majority of scholars believe that it was a series of texts or traditions compiled, others believe it was written as a single document.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Rewards are reserved for the eschaton when the righteous will be resurrected.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: The text wants members to adhere to the commandments of Torah, but is lenient in enforcing this.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: See prayers of gratitude in the Eucharist in chapters 9-10

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Required to lead the life of righteousness in chapter 1.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: To distinguish false prophets from true prophets in chapter 11.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents must fast before baptism and twice a week every week, on "the fourth day and on the Preparation day [for the Sabbath] (8:1)."

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The document contains many ethical precepts designed to shape the behavior of community members. Chapter 1 begins this with the Two Ways discourse and Chapter 2 directly references the 10 commandments.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: New Testament apocrypha

Notes: The Didache now falls squarely into the category of New Testament apocrypha, defined as writings that were ultimately not granted scriptural status. Evidence of its early canonicity can be found in how many ancient authors quote from it, including Irenaeus and Origen of Alexandria. By the 4th century, however, several ancient authors such as Athanasius of Alexandria and Eusebius of Caesarea considered it edifying but not scriptural.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: There is nothing resembling an annual calendar. There are, nevertheless, regular rituals such as fasting twice a week and praying The Lord's Prayer three times a day.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text does not address funerary practices.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibits eating food offered to idols and says that members should try to follow the food laws of the Torah (6:2-3).

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: While angels play a prominent part in both Jewish and Christian lore, this text does not speak of them.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: While the text does not speak of the presence of the dead, it does affirm that at the eschaton the righteous who have died will be resurrected.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents must pray The Lord's Prayer 3 times daily and before and after the Eucharistic meal (the text doesn't specify how often the Eucharist is to be taken).

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text does baptize in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit but most would not consider this a pantheon.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: While the canonical gospels seem to see Jesus as a god-man, this text generally calls Jesus God's servant.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The first four chapters are ethical precepts. Following the decalogue is mandatory. Much of the ethical precepts from Matthew's sermon on the mount are also present, although we don't know if the Didachist drew this material from Matthew, Matthew drew from the Didachist, or they both drew from another source.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: In fact, the text prohibits divination as sinful: "Be neither an enchanter, nor an astrologer, nor a purifier, nor be willing to look at these things, for out of all these idolatry is engendered."

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to know. There is a sense that the rituals are mostly communal.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: Exact times of rituals such as the Eucharist or baptism are not specified in the text.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: This text is an orthopraxy check. It tells how to practice rituals and other practices correctly.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Notes: The author repeatedly calls the reader "my child." This is the only fictive kinship language in the document.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: While rituals are prescribed, the space within which they are performed is not described.

Context

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↳ Other

– Other [specify]: New Testament apocrypha

Notes: The Didache now falls squarely into the category of New Testament apocrypha, defined as writings that were ultimately not granted scriptural status. Evidence of its early canonicity can be found in how many ancient authors quote from it, including Irenaeus and Origen of Alexandria. By the 4th century, however, several ancient authors such as Athanasius of Alexandria and Eusebius of Caesarea considered it edifying but not scriptural.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: There four chapters on rituals and how to perform them correctly (7-10). These include baptism, fasting, prayer, and the Eucharist. However, the Didache makes provisions for those who want to perform the rituals but cannot do so perfectly because of adverse conditions. There are, for example, suggestions for different ways to practice baptism when the optimal conditions, flowing water, are not

present.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The lineage established is certainly Jewish, in the sense that the decalogue and other notions like the Two Ways discourse from Jewish tradition are mentioned. However, there is also a second lineage from Jesus, and many of the ethical commands share material with the Sermon on the Mount. Interestingly, unlike in Matthew, none of the commands are explicitly attributed to Jesus. They are instead simply part of the community rule.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The final section of the Didache is a kind of church organization. First in authority are wandering apostles and/or prophets. There are criteria listed for discerning whether these are real or false prophets: If they stay more than two days, act contrary to their teachings, or ask for money they are false prophets. Next are bishops and deacons appointed by the community.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Spiritual Elect

Notes: Prophets and apostles are not permanent parts of the community. Bishops and deacons, however, are chosen by community members. They must be people who are "gentle, not money-loving, truthful, and tested (15:1)."

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: There is nothing resembling an annual calendar. There are, nevertheless, regular rituals such as fasting twice a week and praying The Lord's Prayer three times a day.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Given the context of Second Temple Judaism and Early Christianity, there was likely a spirit-body distinction but the text is not explicit about this.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The last line of the Didache says "Then the world will see the Lord coming upon the clouds of heaven." So while the spatial location of God's realm is above the earth, the afterlife will be heaven coming down to earth.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

Notes: While heaven is above, in the afterlife it will come down to earth.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: There is no specified time but the time of the approaching eschaton will be indicated by signs such as a "world-deceiver" coming and the resurrection of the righteous (16:4).

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text does not address funerary practices.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: While angels play a prominent part in both Jewish and Christian lore, this text does not speak of them.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: While the text does not speak of the presence of the dead, it does affirm that at the eschaton the righteous who have died will be resurrected.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text does baptize in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit but most would not consider this a pantheon.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: While the canonical gospels seem to see Jesus as a god-man, this text generally calls Jesus God's servant.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: In fact, the text prohibits divination as sinful: "Be neither an enchanter, nor an astrologer, nor a purifier, nor be willing to look at these things, for out of all these idolatry is engendered."

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: It is clear that the Two Ways spoken of in the first section of the document speak of those who adhere to prosocial norms (who will be rewarded) and those who do not (who will be punished). The text says that at the eschaton, "then shall the creation of men come into the fire of trial, and many shall be made to stumble and shall perish; but those who endure in their faith shall be saved from under the curse itself."

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Performance of rituals such as prayer, baptism, and the Eucharist absolutely matter to the deity, but there are no sacrificial offerings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

Notes: The Didache says "And concerning food, bear what you are able; but against that which is sacrificed to idols be exceedingly careful; for it is the service of dead gods. (6.3) "Bear what you are able" means to adhere as much as possible to the halakhic food laws, showing that the Torah is still important to this community.

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: The document makes explicit reference to the prohibition on murder from the decalogue (2:2). It also cautions against anger because it can lead to murder, although coreligionists as victims are not specified (3:2).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: The commandment is simply not to murder anyone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: Reference to this prohibition from the decalogue is made.

↳ Incest

– No

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Fornication and pederasty are explicitly forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: In the decalogue section the document prohibits lying (2:5).

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: "Your speech shall not be false, nor empty, but fulfilled by deed (2:5)."

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: There is a reference to new members who either need to have a trade while living in the community or, if they have no trade, must agree to do whatever work the community thinks necessary (12:3-4)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is prohibited in 5:1.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: No references to elders in terms of age, but certainly chapter 11 says to respect true prophets, bishops, and deacons.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Notes: 2:3 repeats the decalogues prohibition on bearing false witness and speaking badly of anyone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Notes: Again from the decalogue, stealing is prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: The document seems to imply that the deity only expects adherents to do their best: "For if you are able to bear the entire yoke of the Lord [the Torah], you will be perfect; but if you are not able to do this, do what you are able (6:2)."

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: These include baptism, fasting, prayer, and the eucharist.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly demonstrated in the injunction to give to the poor (1:6)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment seems to be that the unrighteous shall simply remain dead rather than being resurrected (16:7).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Rewards are reserved for the eschaton when the righteous will be resurrected.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: In chapter 16, there are simply signs that will appear when he is about to return.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Again, signs will appear indicating the imminent end of the age.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: The community is told to look for certain signs: "For in the last days false prophets and corrupters shall be multiplied, and the sheep shall be turned into wolves, and love shall be turned into hate; for when lawlessness increases, they shall hate and persecute and betray one another, and then shall appear the world-deceiver as Son of God, and shall do signs and wonders, and the earth shall be delivered into his hands, and he shall do iniquitous things which have never yet come to pass since the beginning (16:3-4).

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Not much is said explicitly about this, but the righteous will live or be resurrected if they have died and the unrighteous will die or stay dead.

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Notes: This is implied in the coming of the Lord and the resurrection of the faithful, although the language of "restoration of the world" is not used. See 16:7-8.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Specifically those who have remained faithful (16:5).

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Again, those who have remained faithful.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The 10 commandments are invoked in chapter 2, along with more specific rules in chapter 1.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: Eating food offered to idols was a general cultural practice in the Roman world, but the Didache community are told not to do it.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: The common Jewish discourse of the Two Ways, one good and one evil, are invoked by listing what each one does in Chapter 1.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Again, see the reproduced decalogue in chapter 2.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: This community believes that their deity is universal and thus all norms prescribed by the deity should be followed by everyone, even though this document is specifically written only for the community.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: The text wants members to adhere to the commandments of Torah, but is lenient in enforcing this.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
 - Notes: See prayers of gratitude in the Eucharist in chapters 9-10
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
 - Notes: Required to lead the life of righteousness in chapter 1.
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: To distinguish false prophets from true prophets in chapter 11.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text forbids adultery and fornication, but says nothing about sex within marriage.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

Notes: Since adultery and sex outside marriage (fornication) are prohibited, we can assume that monogamy is allowed.

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Notes: The text does not specify (or even address) marriage, but since adultery and fornication are forbidden, we can assume that monogamy is encouraged.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents must fast before baptism and twice a week every week, on "the fourth day and on the Preparation day [for the Sabbath] (8:1)."

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibits eating food offered to idols and says that members should try to follow the food laws of the Torah (6:2-3).

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents must pray The Lord's Prayer 3 times daily and before and after the Eucharistic meal (the text doesn't specify how often the Eucharist is to be taken).

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The first four chapters are ethical precepts. Following the decalogue is mandatory. Much of the ethical precepts from Matthew's sermon on the mount are also present, although we don't know if the Didachist drew this material from Matthew, Matthew drew from the Didachist, or they both drew from another source.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to know. There is a sense that the rituals are mostly communal.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: Exact times of rituals such as the Eucharist or baptism are not specified in the text.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: This text is an orthopraxy check. It tells how to practice rituals and other practices correctly.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Notes: The author repeatedly calls the reader "my child." This is the only fictive kinship language in the document.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: While rituals are prescribed, the space within which they are performed is not described.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: The closest thing to bureaucracy in the text is the appointment of bishops and deacons. What those bishops and deacons are responsible for is not mentioned.

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Notes: There are not many details about the community in the text. However, it is clear that they accept new members who have come to the faith.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: While food rules and restrictions are present, food distribution is not addressed, except in the case of wandering prophets who are to be fed.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: There is nothing written in the text about formal education.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: 1:5 encouraging giving to everyone who asks. There is also a phrase in 1:6 which seems to encourage charity, although it is a bit unclear: "Let your alms sweat in your hands, until you know to whom you should give."

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– I don't know

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Hospitality for wandering prophets.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Wandering prophets are said to teach in the religious realm. The text says that if they are true prophets that members should listen to their teaching.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

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Public Works

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Warfare

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